

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

Nietalina G.

PhD, Associate Professor

Turan University, Almaty

Adilgery A.

doctoral student of the DBA program

Turan University, Almaty

Abstract

The article considers the mechanism of organization of public services in Kazakhstan. The ideas on the active participation of citizens in the improvement of public service are substantiated. Increasing customer orientation, development of public-private partnership (PPP). Measures for automation and digitalization of the public sector are proposed. Work is needed to strengthen the personnel policy in the field of public service, to strengthen the motivation of civil servants.

Keywords: public services, digitalization of the public sector, civil servants, PPP.

Kazakhstan has achieved success in building the concept of e-government, providing electronic public services, which has improved access to information and reduced the risks of corruption. At the same time, signs of a systematic improvement in the effective organization of the activities of state bodies for the high-quality provision of public services require serious improvement. In our opinion, measures are required to improve the mechanism for organizing the provision of public services in Kazakhstan.

The mechanism for organizing the provision of public services in Kazakhstan is presented in the form of the following scheme, which includes several blocks, according to Figure 1.

First, we consider it important that government agencies build business processes of interaction with service recipients based on the needs of service recipients.

Many service recipients, especially the older generation, do not use the opportunities for easier and more comfortable receipt of public services in electronic format [1]. In addition, there is low civic engagement among the population. There is no conscious and active position of citizens that can influence the improvement of the quality of services provided.

Therefore, the first block in the mechanism of effective organization of public services in Kazakhstan is quite objectively carrying out work to strengthen and widely involve citizens in improving public service in the country.

In our opinion, an important block in the systemic mechanism of the organization of public services in Kazakhstan is customer orientation as a factor in the implementation of the "Hearing State".

Figure 1. The mechanism of organization of public services in Kazakhstan

Note: compiled by the authors.

Another unresolved problem in recent years has been the technical problems of electronic services and websites providing public services. Public-private partnership (PPP) plays an important role in solving problems. The state services "Registration of an individual entrepreneur" and "Re-registration of a car" are available via Kaspi.kz. Today, these services are provided in a proactive format and are popular among citizens [2].

An important direction of the mechanism of organization of public services in Kazakhstan is further automation and digitalization of the public sphere, which is presented by the name in the form of block IV.

During his participation in the international technology forum Digital Bridge, the President of Kazakhstan K.-Zh. Tokayev defined the guidelines for the prospects of digitalization of public services in the country. The Head of State pointed out the importance of constantly updating the content of public services: "The task is not just to convert services from offline to online. The "figure" should reduce the very number of public services and related requests, responses, approvals. Public services should be comprehensive and proactive," K.-Zh. Tokayev [3].

In general, we believe that the digital transformation of government agencies should be considered as a tool to combat bureaucracy, corruption and inefficiency.

In blocks V and VI, we recommend that work be carried out to strengthen the personnel policy in the field of public service, as well as to increase motivation for young people to work, especially in public services in districts and villages of Kazakhstan.

Thus, further improvement of the procedures for selecting candidates for public service is required. To

ensure transparency of the selection process, work will be carried out to fully digitalize the competitive procedures. So, by the end of 2024, all stages of selection in the E-kyzmet information system will be automated. The initiative of the Head of State on the formation of the Presidential Youth Personnel Reserve (PYPR) is being implemented [4].

An important block is the motivational block in the mechanism of public administration. Thus, a fair system of remuneration for civil servants is needed, considering their contribution and effectiveness, as well as the complexity and specifics of the work performed.

It is necessary to further bring the level of salaries of employees closer to the private sector, to level the difference in official salaries between the center and the regions and, in general, to increase the attractiveness of the civil service.

So, in the process of forming a mechanism for organizing the provision of public services at a high level, the main thing must be considered - to make services accessible, high-quality, convenient, and fast for the people.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the mechanisms for the effective organization of the provision of public services may include the following elements:

1. Development and optimization of public service delivery processes using modern methods of quality management and efficiency improvement.

2. Simplification of procedures and bureaucratic formalities to ensure the convenience and speed of the provision of public services.

3. Creation of electronic platforms for the provision of public services that ensure accessibility and ease of use for the public.

4. Establishing clear standards, requirements and quality indicators for the provision of public services that ensure their high quality and level.

5. Organization of a feedback system and monitoring of the quality of public services to continuously improve their quality.

6. Training and advanced training of civil servants working with the public, according to the principles of customer orientation and quality service.

References

1. The main problems in the field of public services in Kazakhstan are named. [electronic resource].

URL: <https://zonakz.net/2018/11/12/nazvany-osnovnye-problemy-v-sfere-gosuslug-v-kazaxstane/> (date of access: 06/10/2024)

2. Abylkhasanova, N.E. Improving the quality of public services through the introduction of digitalization. [electronic resource]. URL: <https://repository.apa.kz/xmlui/handle/123456789/886> (date of application: 06/11/2024)

3. Digitalization against corruption. [electronic resource]. URL: <https://ru.sputnik.kz/20211027/TsifrUovizatsiya-dolzha-byt-instrumentom-borby-s-byurokatiy-i-korrupsiy--Tokaev-18515785.html> (date of access: 06/10/2024)

4. How the Presidential Youth Personnel Reserve reveals the potential of Kazakhstanis. [electronic resource]. URL: <http://tengrinews.kz/story/prezidentskiy-molodejnyiy-kadrovyy-rezerv-raskryivaet-409727/amp/> (date of access: 06/11/2024)